

Leishmaniasis: A Serious Public Health Concern in Pakistan

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Abstract

Leishmaniasis is a major public health concern, owing to both environmental and individual risk factors, such as large migrations, urbanization, deforestation, and new irrigation schemes. It is a disease of tropical and subtropical regions of Asia, Africa, America, and the Mediterranean. The causative agent *Leishmania* is transmitted in humans through the bite of sandfly (*Phlebotomus* and *Lutzomyia* species). The disease is ranked among the top seven deadly diseases of public health significance by the World Health Organization (WHO). Every year, 1.5 to 2 million new cases are reported worldwide; 350 million people are at risk of contracting the disease, and 70,000 people die from leishmaniasis. Clinical symptoms encompass a wide spectrum of signs with varying degrees of severity depending on the *Leishmania* species involved and the immune status of the host. The symptoms range from localized cutaneous to visceral and potentially lethal consequences. The disease manifests itself in a variety of ways, ranging from self-limited and even self-healing cutaneous manifestations to severe systemic disease, i.e., spleen and liver, etc. Lesions of leishmaniasis can appear everywhere on the body; however, the exposed areas are prone to attack. Although

the organism that causes leishmaniasis was discovered 100 years ago, the disease has not been eradicated, and in many parts of the world, it is on the rise. It has the potential to become a severe health issue if no control measures are taken. The cutaneous form of leishmaniasis is common in various regions of Pakistan, including South Punjab, KPK, Baluchistan, Sindh, and tribal areas. It is the second most prevalent vector-borne disease in Pakistan after malaria. Several factors such as climatic and environmental changes, the movement or migration of infected people, animal reservoirs, and female infected sandflies play an important role in the transmission of leishmaniasis. Keeping in view the significance of this public health threat, studies should be carried out in the endemic areas of Pakistan. Reservoir hosts, humans, and other risk factors responsible for the transmission of disease in vectors and hosts must be quantified with the objective of informing policymakers to make evidence-based control strategies to combat this disease.

Keywords: Leishmaniasis, Vector-borne disease, Sandfly, Zoonosis, Reservoir hosts